

SUPERSHINE

D5.2 Policy Reviews and Prospects for Social Housing in the Fellow City Countries and Regions - Part 2

Authors: Esra Demir (DEMIR); Buse Araç (DEMIR); Paola Zerilli (UoY); Ahmed Djeddi (UoY); Isabel Rodríguez (ENA); Cristina Daniel (ENA); Orlando Paraíba (ENA); Ricardo Alegria (ENA); Aranzazu Fernández (ZV); Erdem Kocabey (KM); Alice Pittini (HE)

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1. Technical references

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AVS	Asociación Española de Gestores Públicos de Vivienda y Suelo (Association of Public Managers of Housing and Land)
BL	Boligselskabernes Landsforening
CONCOVI	Confederación de Cooperativas de Viviendas de España (Confederation of Housing Cooperatives of Spain)
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
ERP	Edilizia Residenziale Pubblica (Public Residential Housing)
EU	European Union
EU SHAI	The European Union Support to Social Housing and Active Inclusion Programme
FHS	Fondazione Housing Sociale (Social Housing Foundation)
NEEF	National Energy Efficiency Fund
IBI	Impuesto sobre Bienes Inmuebles (Property Tax)
IFRRU 2020	Instrumento Financeiro para a Reabilitação e Revitalização Urbanas (Financial Instrument for Urban Rehabilitation and Revitalization)
PAH	Plataforma de Afectadas por la Hipoteca (Platform of Mortgage Affected People)
PER	Programa Especial de Realojamento (Rehousing Special Programme)
PRR	Plano de Recuperação e Resiliência (Recovery and Resilience Plan)

SAREB	Sociedad de Gestión de Activos Procedentes de la Reestructuración Bancaria (Asset Management Company from the Banking Restructuring)
TOKİ	Toplu Konut İdaresi Başkanlığı (Housing Development Administration of the Republic of Türkiye)
VARAM	Vides Aizsardzības un Reģionālās Attīstības Ministrija (Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development)

2. Executive Summary

This report, *D5.2 - Policy Reviews and Prospects for Social Housing in the Fellow City Countries and Regions – Part 2*, provides an in-depth analysis of social housing policies and developments across SUPERSHINE’s fellow and lighthouse cities. Building on Part 1, which examined the historical context and current landscape in fellow cities - Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), Belgrade (Serbia), and Istanbul (Türkiye) -, Part 2 extends the review to lighthouse cities, assessing their recent policies, challenges, and socioeconomic dynamics.

The report highlights common challenges in social housing, such as aging infrastructure, financial constraints, and affordability concerns, while showcasing how cities are addressing these issues through retrofitting, policy integration, and innovative funding mechanisms. Lighthouse cities and their respective countries, Herning (Denmark), Trieste (Italy), and Riga (Latvia), serve as models of best practices. Denmark emphasises tenant participation (with their peculiar “tenant democracy”), sustainability, and crisis response; Italy’s cooperative housing model fosters affordability and social cohesion; and Latvia demonstrates effective municipal-led management and energy-efficient solutions.

By analysing these diverse approaches, the report provides valuable insights into how social housing systems can be improved to align with broader EU objectives of sustainability, inclusivity, and affordability. The knowledge exchange between lighthouse and fellow cities supports the adaptation and scaling of successful strategies, promoting a more resilient and equitable housing sector across Europe.

3. Introduction

3.1. Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to provide a detailed examination of social housing policies, reviews and prospects in the fellow cities and lighthouses. In Part 1 of this report, we have reviewed the historical context and current landscape of social housing across the fellow cities – Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), Belgrade (Serbia) and Istanbul (Türkiye) - highlighting the unique approaches and challenges faced by each. This provides a comprehensive overview of the social housing policies and practices in the respective regions, helping to understand the diverse frameworks in place.

As we move forward to Part 2, the historical background, recent policies, developments, and challenges of the lighthouse cities are included. Socioeconomic aspects and city-level policy reviews for both lighthouse cities and fellow cities are also conducted, providing insights into how local policies and social factors impact social housing and guide future improvements. This analysis will help us better understand the challenges and opportunities in social housing, focusing on how local policies and social factors affect housing programs. The findings from these investigations will help guide future strategies for improving social housing systems in line with broader urban development goals.

3.2. Interdependencies with Other WPs and Tasks

The findings from WP1, especially the results from D1.1, provided important input for this section, particularly on socioeconomic aspects. This included valuable information on both lighthouse and fellow cities. In addition, data collected from surveys in WP2 helped to better understand the financial, environmental, and social aspects of the cities. These insights were used to develop this document and ensure a comprehensive assessment. The information gathered in this section will also support ongoing and future tasks in WP5, keeping it aligned with the overall project goals.

4. EU Targets and Policies

The European Union (EU) has set targets for reducing its greenhouse gas emissions progressively up to 2050 by means of the 2020 climate and energy package, the 2030 climate and energy framework, and the 2050 long-term strategy. Sustainable construction is expected to play a big part in meeting the European Union's climate and energy goals since the built environment is estimated to account for approximately 40% of energy consumption and 36% of CO₂ emissions in the EU. Sustainable, climate-proofed buildings are needed on a massive scale to meet the objectives for 2030 and to achieve a climate-neutral Europe by 2050.

The current energy crisis accompanied by the political distress in the Eastern Europe area have added significantly to the increase in electricity and gas prices which has affected the livelihood of millions of households in the EU, and since the global expansion in early 2020 of the COVID-19 pandemic, the energy crisis has exponentially increased the pre-existing issues of energy poverty in social and affordable housing, as inhabitants in EU countries enforcing lockdowns were more likely to spend more time at home increasing their energy consumption and became more vulnerable to energy poverty.

In the case of the population with income status below 60% of the median equivalised income, the statistics say that residents in Türkiye, Portugal and Latvia have the highest rates of energy poverty. It is important to acknowledge that the statistics about energy poverty is not promising and vary in different EU countries due to the differences about policies, regulations, demographic, socio economic structure.

According to statistics from EU nearly half of the population who are below 60% of median equivalised income is unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status in Türkiye while it is nearly 30% for Portugal, Serbia and Spain¹. According to the same report the arrears on utility bills are over 20% for Serbia and Türkiye.

Although there has been a decrease in material and social deprivation rate since 2011 it is still over 10% for Italy, Latvia, Portugal, Spain and Serbia (over20%). The rates in Türkiye are above 30% being the highest among the consortium countries. These rates are even much higher among tenants.

In July 2021, as part of the European Green Deal package, the Commission introduced a proposal to revamp the Energy Efficiency Directive, supporting the EU's objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. It put forward a stronger and

¹ SUPERSHINE Project, D1.1: Landscape of socio economic context

binding EU energy efficiency target of 9% for 2030, compared to the projections of the 2020 Reference Scenario (787 Mtoe in final and 1 023 Mtoe in primary energy consumption, respectively). This proposal corresponded to a reduction of 36% in final energy consumption and 39% in primary energy consumption by 2030, compared to the 2007 Reference Scenario. The final target of 11.7% agreed by the co-legislators, which entered into force on 10 October 2023.

There are a number EU rules and initiatives to achieve a fully decarbonised building stock by 2050.

- Energy Performance of Buildings Directive: The directive sets out a range of measures to help boost the energy efficiency of buildings across Europe.
- Nearly-zero energy and zero-emission buildings: EU standards to ensure all new buildings have a high energy performance and very low energy needs.
- Renovation Wave: Renovating the EU building stock will improve energy efficiency while driving the clean energy transition.
- EU Building Stock Observatory: The EU Building Stock Observatory (BSO) web tool monitors the energy performance of buildings across Europe.
- Smart readiness indicator: The smart readiness indicator rating of a building depends on its capacity to accommodate smart-ready services. The introduction of the Directives was also an enabler in accelerating the efforts.
- National Building Renovation Plans: Ensuring the achievement of a highly energy-efficient and decarbonised building stock by 2050.

The funding mechanisms mobilised since energy efficiency is one of the priorities of European countries has increased during the last decade. The Innovation Fund, Just Transition Mechanism, Horizon Europe, LIFE Program, etc all serve to combat climate change. Energy poverty remains a major challenge that needs to be tackled both in developing and developed countries. Public, cooperative, and social housing providers have already started working on the issue. Some of their homes achieve better average energy performance than any other segment of the housing market in many parts of Europe, ensuring comfort at an affordable price for the primarily low-income families they serve.

5. Insights From Policy Reviews on Social Housing of Fellow Cities- Part 1

Social housing plays a key role in providing affordable housing for those in need, but its structure, management, and purpose vary across countries. It refers to housing provided at affordable rates to support individuals and families who may struggle to access housing in the private market. Typically, it is funded, regulated, or managed by public authorities, non-profit organizations, or housing cooperatives. The main objectives of social housing include ensuring access to decent living conditions, preventing homelessness, and promoting social inclusion.

Each country sets its own policies based on specific target groups and eligibility criteria, shaping how social housing is allocated and maintained. As the sector evolves, there is a growing emphasis on local decision-making and adapting policies to changing needs.

In the first part of this deliverable, the focus was on the fellow cities' case reporting. This included a historical background of social housing in each country, recent policies and developments, as well as the challenges faced in the sector. Additionally, funding sources and relevant initiatives were discussed. The national context of the countries of the SUPERSHINE Fellow cities, Spain, Portugal, Serbia and Türkiye, were examined in detail to understand the diverse approaches and strategies employed in each context. A summary of the findings can be found in this section.

5.1. Spain

Spain's housing policies have evolved over time. During the Franco Era, the state encouraged home ownership by promoting affordable housing for sale, often with basic standards. With democracy, policies became decentralized, improving housing quality and homeownership. A property boom from the late 1990s to 2008 prioritized private ownership, but the 2008 financial crisis led to a market crash, evictions and empty homes.

Following the crisis, the Platform of Mortgage Affected People (PAH) emerged to advocate for those facing eviction. In Spain, various institutions, associations, and cooperatives play a role in social housing. Organizations like Association of Public Managers of Housing and Land (AVS), which brings together local public housing and land development companies from across the country, and Confederation of Housing Cooperatives of Spain (CONCOVI), which supports housing cooperatives, play key roles in Spain's housing sector.²

² The State of the Housing in Europe 2023 [Review of The State of the Housing in Europe 2023]. (2023) Housing Europe's Observatory, 82. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1825/the-state-of-the-housing-in-europe-2023>

Additionally, a new law mandates that 30% of new developments be reserved for subsidized housing, with 15% allocated to social renting, aiming to expand public housing and strengthen protections for vulnerable individuals.

Despite ongoing efforts, social housing in Spain also faces several challenges such as diverse needs, limited stock, gentrification, economic constraints, legal hurdles, and environmental concerns.

In Spain, several funding sources and initiatives support energy efficiency renovation projects, including the National Energy Efficiency Fund (Fondo Nacional de Eficiencia Energética), the Programa de Ayudas para la Rehabilitación Energética de Edificios (Program for Energy Renovation of Buildings), and the Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE).

5.2. Portugal

Social housing policies in Portugal have evolved significantly, reflecting political, economic, and social changes. Before the 20th century, housing was mainly based on charity, with little state involvement. Under the Estado Novo regime (1933-1974), the state began intervening in housing, focusing on slum clearance and providing affordable housing, including workers' neighbourhoods and the "Casa Portuguesa" model, which combined traditional and functional design, an approach closely tied to the regime's efforts to maintain social control.

After the 1974 Carnation Revolution, the new democratic government shifted to prioritise social welfare, enshrining the right to housing in the 1976 Constitution. Public housing expanded, particularly in peripheral urban areas in major cities, with a focus on mass housing for lower and middle-income groups. In the 1990s and 2000s, housing policies evolved further, influenced by the EU, with programmes like the Rehousing Special Programme (PER), which aimed to replace informal settlements with modern housing. Public-private partnerships reduced direct public investment in social housing, promoting market-driven solutions.

Social housing, estimated to represent about 2% of the housing stock in the country, is mainly provided by municipalities (the largest social housing stock being in Lisbon and Porto), and to a lesser extent by cooperatives and charitable institutions. The Institute for Housing and Urban Renewal (IRHU) also owns and manages about 14 thousand dwellings across the country, and at the same time is the main agency channelling state funding to the sector through a number of programmes.

More recent initiatives include Porta 65, which subsidises rent for young people aged 18-35, and a growing focus on urban rehabilitation through programmes like IFRRU 2020, which finances the transformation of buildings into energy-efficient spaces. Despite these

advancements, challenges persist, including a housing shortage, rising prices driven by tourism, and ageing infrastructure. Economic constraints, land speculation, and difficulties in societal integration add layers of complexity to the efforts to meet the housing needs.

Portugal has introduced several funding initiatives to improve housing and energy efficiency, such as the Portuguese Environmental Fund, the Energy Efficiency Fund, and the Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Housing Program. In 2024, the government approved a long-term strategy to combat energy poverty (ELPPE 2023-2050), and in 2025, established a national network of energy spaces (one-stop-shops), coordinated by the National Energy Agency, to enhance energy efficiency in homes, particularly those occupied by vulnerable families.

5.3. Serbia

During the Yugoslavia era, housing focused on homeownership, with limited rental social housing. After the 1990s breakup, conflicts caused housing damage and informal settlements. The 2006 Law on Social Housing marked a shift, but challenges like limited funding and housing issues for vulnerable groups persist.

Recent policies and developments in social housing in Serbia reflect a concerted effort to address the needs of vulnerable populations and revitalise both urban and rural areas. The 2006 Law on Social Housing established a legal framework targeting vulnerable groups. Initiatives like the EU SHAI Program focus on providing housing for survivors of domestic violence, young adults and people with disabilities. The "Leaving No One Behind" project in Čačak provided social housing for 12 families. Additionally, the Rural Housing Scheme promotes rural rejuvenation by offering non-repayable funds for purchasing rural homes. Serbia's social housing faces challenges such as implementation issues, economic constraints, informal settlements, vulnerable populations, stigma and legal/regulatory hurdles.

In Serbia, there are various funding sources and initiatives available for energy efficiency renovation projects, aimed at improving the energy performance of buildings and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Some of these include National Energy Efficiency Fund (NEEF), European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), Green for Growth Fund (GGF) along with regional and municipal programs.

5.4. Türkiye

In Türkiye, early social housing policy involved direct state intervention, with the government constructing residences (lojmans) for public employees to improve living conditions. After

WWII, rapid urbanization led to a housing shortage, and informal squatter neighbourhoods emerged. The First Squatter Housing Law was enacted in 1966, alongside the First and Second Housing Laws. This period also saw the establishment of the Housing Development Administration of the Republic of Türkiye (TOKİ), which, in collaboration with the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, became key in housing policies.

Until the 2000s, Türkiye's welfare system relied on informal provisions, with TOKİ becoming the main housing provider. Over time, housing projects shifted focus towards the middle class, leaving low-income groups with limited access to formal housing. Despite efforts to expand social housing, several challenges persist in Türkiye's housing sector such as limited affordability, gentrification, regulatory and bureaucratic issues.

In addition to the challenges, several funding sources are available to support social housing initiatives, such as KOSGEB (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Organization), TÜBİTAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye, and İller Bankası (Provincial Bank), which provide essential financial resources for housing projects.

Kadıköy does not follow a traditional social housing model as seen in many European cities, where municipalities or the state directly provide affordable rental housing. Instead, the district primarily consists of privately owned residential buildings, with urban renewal largely driven by private sector contractors under market-based principles. While some areas with aging and unsafe building stock have been designated as Special Project Areas for redevelopment, these projects are often shaped by real estate market dynamics rather than a non-profit, social housing approach. Unlike municipalities that maintain a public housing stock, Kadıköy lacks a structured system of municipal-led affordable housing, relying instead on individual property owners and private developers for urban transformation. This results in rising property values and gentrification, limiting housing accessibility for lower-income groups. To address this, alternative policies such as cooperative housing models, rent-controlled developments, and municipal intervention in renewal projects could be explored to promote more inclusive and affordable housing solutions.

6. Fellow Cities Socio-Economic Structure and Social Housing Retrofit Policies

In the first part of the Task 5.1 historical background of social housing, recent policies, challenges, funding initiatives were explained for the four follower countries. In this section the latest developments in the cities will be investigated.

6.1. Spain, Zaragoza

Zaragoza, the capital of the Aragón region, has experienced notable economic growth in recent years. The city boasts a diverse industrial base, with significant contributions from the metal and automotive sectors, including a major automotive manufacturing plant. In 2023, Zaragoza's exports totalled €13.8 billion, positioning it fifth among Spanish provinces in both exports and imports. a 2024 report highlighted Zaragoza as the Spanish city with the highest well-being index among capitals with over 500,000 inhabitants, surpassing both Barcelona and Madrid.^{3, 4}

Zaragoza, has an aging housing stock – over half of its 326,000 dwellings were built before 1981. Many of the mid-20th-century apartment blocks (often four-story walk-ups from the 1960s) suffer from poor thermal insulation and lack basic accessibility features. Social housing itself is a small portion (under 1% of homes),⁵ but much of it falls into this older, energy-inefficient category. In recent years, authorities have recognized the need to retrofit these buildings to improve energy efficiency, structural safety, and accessibility.

Zaragoza has been actively addressing social housing needs through various initiatives and developments. The city has seen the construction of numerous social housing projects, often in collaboration with architectural firms. Zaragoza's municipal housing agency Sociedad Municipal Zaragoza Vivienda (ZV) has accordingly developed a plan to invest in energy-efficient renovations through 2030. Multiple initiatives – from local grant programs to European-funded projects – are now underway to upgrade social housing conditions.

Zaragoza's push to retrofit social and low-income housing has gained momentum in the past few years, and recent developments indicate a strong commitment to continue these upgrades. In 2022, Zaragoza was selected by the European Commission as one of the 100 Climate-Neutral Cities by 2030, a mission that has reinforced local retrofit initiatives. As part

³ Zaragoza - Eurocities. (2020, August 6). Eurocities - Home. <https://eurocities.eu/cities/zaragoza/>

⁴ SER, C. (2025, March 4). *El paro baja en Aragón en 143 personas en febrero*. Cadena SER. <https://cadenaser.com/aragon/2025/03/04/el-paro-baja-en-aragon-en-143-personas-en-febrero-radio-zaragoza/>

⁵ *Sharing knowledge for efficient renovation of residential buildings in Zaragoza*. (2024, October 24). SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/hubs/sharing-knowledge-efficient-renovation-residential-buildings-zaragoza>

of its climate action plan, Zaragoza has set a target to renovate 3,000 homes by 2030 to sharply reduce their thermal energy consumption. Several new funding injections and pilot projects have been announced recently. Zaragoza Vivienda's 2030 plan will continue targeting the most vulnerable neighbourhoods and scaling up successful pilots citywide.⁶

In recent years, efforts have intensified to provide affordable housing, especially for young people. In January 2025, it was announced that near 1,070 affordable rental units would be available by 2027, offering rents between €341 and €566 per month.⁷

However, challenges persist. In February 2025, the Sociedad de Gestión de Activos Procedentes de la Reestructuración Bancaria (SAREB) reissued a call for the construction of affordable housing in Zaragoza after the initial tender in January received no bids. This situation highlights the complexities involved in mobilizing resources for social housing projects. And in the February 2025, ZV had to acquire a 27 unit building to prevent vulnerable families living there from being at risk of eviction as a result of the change in leases associated with the change in ownership of the building.⁸

To further support affordable housing, political leaders have proposed measures such as property tax (IBI) reductions in cities governed by the Partido Popular (PP). These initiatives aim to ease access to housing for various demographics, including young people and vulnerable groups.

6.2. Portugal, Setúbal

Setúbal has a diverse socio-economic structure, with key industries in shipbuilding, harbour operations, agri-food, fishing, and wine production. Tourism and the service sector are expanding, driven by proximity to Lisbon and the Arrábida Natural Park. The city faces social contrasts, with both vulnerable neighbourhoods and upper-middle-class housing. Unemployment has decreased, though job insecurity remains.

The municipality has a strong history of social housing initiatives and is actively retrofitting its housing stock, prioritising energy efficiency and sustainability. In collaboration with the Central Administration, it has promoted the construction of numerous affordable and social housing units. The Special Rehousing Programme (PER) has provided decent homes for around 1,000 families, and the Municipal Council now manages approximately 2,300 social

⁶ Lisbona, J. (2023, September 29). *Zaragoza rehabilitará 40 viviendas en Balsas de Ebro Viejo a través de un proyecto piloto de la UE*. Herald.es; Herald de Aragón. <https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/aragon/zaragoza/2023/09/29/zaragoza-rehabilitara-40-viviendas-en-balsas-de-ebro-viejo-a-traves-de-un-proyecto-piloto-de-la-ue-1680862.html>

⁷ *Zaragoza Vivienda*. (2025). ZaragozaVivienda.es. <https://www.zaragozavivienda.es/noticias.asp?id=620#gsc.tab=0>

⁸ Poveda, I. (2025, March 7). *El Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza compra un edificio por dos millones de euros para evitar el desahucio de 27 familias*. ELMUNDO; El Mundo.

<https://www.elmundo.es/aragon/2025/03/07/67caeed2e85ece3c788b4581.html>

housing units. Access to public housing follows a regulated, application-based process since 2018.

In October 2023, Setúbal launched a pilot cooperative housing project aiming to construct approximately 50 affordable homes. This initiative is a collaboration between the municipal housing council and the Institute of Housing and Urban Rehabilitation, reflecting a commitment to innovative housing solutions.

As part of the Local Housing Strategy 2020-2030, the municipality is renovating 3,560 existing homes (115M€) and constructing 4,650 new affordable units (264M€) funded by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR). The Municipal Public Housing Rehabilitation Programme includes improvements such as waterproofing, roof repairs, thermal and energy efficiency upgrades and enhancements to shared spaces.

Energy efficiency in municipal public housing is a priority, with 293 homes already certified and plans to extend certification to 1,800 more. Public authorities offer financial support in terms of grants to energy efficiency renovation in social housing level (D1.1). However, challenges remain, including high demand, long waiting lists, and the need for further investment in infrastructure. The lack of private investment is a key concern, requiring continued financial support and sustainable retrofitting solutions.

6.3. Serbia, Belgrade

Belgrade, Serbia's capital, is the nation's economic and political center. The Serbian economy is classified as an upper-middle-income, service-based economy, with the tertiary sector accounting for two-thirds of the GDP.

In the first half of 2024, Serbia's economic growth accelerated, leading to an increased projected GDP growth of 3.8% for the year, attributed to strong performances in construction and services. However, challenges persist, including high unemployment rates and income inequality, with nearly a quarter of the population at risk of poverty and social exclusion. Belgrade has also been a focal point for recent protests addressing issues such as government corruption and unsafe construction practices, reflecting ongoing socio-political dynamics.

Belgrade, Serbia's capital, is actively engaging in retrofitting its social housing stock, particularly focusing on structures from the socialist era that now require modernization to meet current energy efficiency and living standards.

In early 2019, Belgrade saw the formation of its first housing co-operative, named "Pametnija Zgrada" (Smarter Building). This initiative aims to develop a pilot project comprising approximately 20 housing units and communal spaces, fostering community

living and collaborative housing solutions.⁹ Belgrade has undertaken projects to provide housing for marginalized groups. One such project involved constructing a building with 15 flats in the Jabučki Rit area, specifically designed for vulnerable Roma families relocated from informal settlements. This initiative is part of the broader "Let's Build a Home Together" program, funded by the European Union and implemented in collaboration with various partners.

Despite these initiatives, challenges persist in scaling up retrofitting efforts across Belgrade's extensive social housing stock. Many buildings require significant investment to address structural deficiencies, improve energy efficiency, and enhance accessibility. Securing adequate funding, fostering public-private partnerships, and raising awareness about the benefits of retrofitting are crucial steps toward sustainable urban development in Belgrade.

6.4. Türkiye, Kadıköy

Kadıköy, located on Istanbul's Asian side, is recognized for its high socio-economic development and educational attainment. Approximately 19% of its population is elderly, reflecting a mature demographic. The district ranks first on Türkiye's Human Development Index and fourth in socio-economic development.

The area has undergone significant socio-spatial changes, with studies indicating a strong relationship between its urban character and factors such as family type, income level, and cultural diversity. Still there are areas where low-income families live and, they usually do not have the means for the renovation or transformation of their buildings.

Many buildings, particularly older structures, require significant investment to meet contemporary energy efficiency standards. Challenges such as high costs, bureaucratic hurdles, and limited financial incentives often hinder retrofitting efforts. Policies should focus on providing financial support through low-interest loans and grants, implementing municipal-led pilot programs, and enforcing stricter retrofitting requirements for high-risk structures.

As part of its urban transformation efforts, Kadıköy has been replacing old, earthquake-prone buildings with modern, safer structures. The Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality's housing development company, KİPTAŞ, has been actively involved in renewing individual buildings, replacing risky structures with new residential and commercial units. However, some neighborhoods, particularly those with high population density, historical significance, and architectural value, are not suitable for large-scale urban transformation. Instead, these areas require targeted improvements in seismic safety and energy efficiency. Given the

⁹ *Belgrade: a new era for housing co-operatives* - World Habitat. (2020). <https://world-habitat.org/news/our-blog/belgrade-a-new-era-for-housing-co-operatives/>

region's earthquake risk, retrofitting is essential for strengthening existing buildings while preserving their cultural and structural integrity. Additionally, many older buildings suffer from poor insulation and inefficient energy use, making energy retrofits equally important.

Kadıköy Municipality has taken steps to provide temporary social housing solutions, particularly for vulnerable groups such as women, low-income individuals, and displaced residents due to urban renewal. For example, the Women's Shelter Initiative converts municipal properties into safe housing for women and children. This pilot project provides temporary housing for women and their children, covering utility expenses and furnishing costs.¹⁰

Securing adequate funding, fostering public-private partnerships, and raising awareness about the benefits of retrofitting are essential steps toward achieving the district's sustainability goals.

¹⁰ Kadıköy Belediyesi Bilgi İşlem Müdürlüğü. (2025). *KADIN YAŞAM EVİ | Kadıköy Belediyesi Sosyal Hizmet Merkezleri*. Kadikoy.bel.tr. <https://sosyaldestek.kadikoy.bel.tr/projeler/kadin-yasam-evi>

7. Policy Reviews on Social Housing for the Countries of the SUPERSHINE lighthouses

In the first part of this report social housing and the policies of the fellow cities were taken into account. After submitting the deliverable, it is realised to see the situation in Lighthouses to be able to have a more insight on the socio-cultural, demographic, economic differences on the policies of retrofitting social housing.

7.1. Denmark

Denmark's social housing system is one of the most structured and well-regulated in Europe, ensuring affordable, high-quality housing for a diverse population. Approximately 20% of the country's housing stock consists of non-profit social housing, primarily managed by self-governing housing associations (almen boligforeninger).¹¹ These associations operate under a democratic model where tenants play an active role in decision-making processes regarding maintenance, renovations and community development.

A key player in Denmark's social housing sector is BL – Boligselskabernes Landsforening, the national federation of social housing organizations. BL represents 452 non-profit housing associations, advocating for policies that ensure affordability, sustainability and social cohesion. The organization also plays a crucial role in coordinating funding mechanisms, promoting best practices and supporting housing providers in addressing challenges such as rising construction costs, urbanization pressures and the need for large-scale energy-efficient renovations. In 2021, BL members completed 4,629 new housing units, contributing to Denmark's total of 35,563 housing completions. Additionally, nearly 40,000 social housing units were renovated to enhance energy efficiency and living standards, reflecting the sector's focus on modernization and sustainability.¹¹

Denmark's social housing system is a well-structured model that ensures affordable, high-quality housing through cooperative management and sustainable practices. As the sector navigates contemporary challenges, it remains focused on fostering inclusive communities and upholding its commitment to social welfare.

¹¹ The State of the Housing in Europe 2023 [Review of The State of the Housing in Europe 2023]. (2023). Housing Europe's Observatory, 45. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1825/the-state-of-the-housing-in-europe-2023>

7.1.1. Historical Background

Denmark's social housing system has its roots in the late 19th-century cooperative movement, where workers and unions established housing associations to provide affordable homes. The state took a more active role in social housing in the 1930s, introducing financial support mechanisms to encourage the construction of affordable rental housing. In 1933, the first Danish act on subsidies for non-profit housing associations was adopted to provide housing for low-income groups. The non-profit housing sector began to take shape with the establishment of housing associations (*almene boliger*), which operated under the principles of affordability, tenant democracy and non-profit ownership. After World War II, Denmark faced a severe housing shortage due to urbanization and population growth. In response, the government significantly expanded its support for social housing, integrating it into the emerging welfare state. The 1946 Housing Act introduced significant subsidies and loans for non-profit housing, making social housing a key component of Denmark's post-war reconstruction efforts. The 1960s and 1970s saw rapid expansion, with modernist high-rise estates designed to improve living conditions. However, concerns over social segregation and urban decay in some areas led to policy shifts in the 1980s, emphasizing rehabilitation, tenant democracy and mixed-income housing. By the late 20th century, Denmark's social housing system had become well-developed and tenant-managed, ensuring affordability while addressing urban planning challenges.

7.1.2. Recent Policies and Development

In recent decades, Denmark's social housing policies have focused on urban renewal, social integration, sustainability and climate adaptation. These policies aim to address challenges such as segregation in vulnerable neighbourhoods, housing affordability and the need for energy-efficient renovations. Denmark has implemented several policies and initiatives to address social housing challenges.

Housing First Strategy: Since 2009, Denmark has used the Housing First approach to reduce homelessness, focusing on providing permanent housing along with personalized support services. In October 2023, key elements of this strategy were incorporated into national legislation, aiming to significantly reduce homelessness and end long-term homelessness. The government has invested significantly in expanding affordable housing and supporting evidence-based programs like Critical Time Intervention (CTI), Intensive Case Management (ICM), and Assertive Community Treatment (ACT) to help people move from shelters to permanent housing.¹²

¹² Denmark - Housing First Europe. (2024, July 2). Housing First Europe. <https://housingfirsteurope.eu/country/denmark/>

Ghetto Plan (Parallel Society Package): Denmark has implemented policies targeting neighbourhoods with high concentrations of non-Western immigrants, aiming to promote social integration and reduce parallel societies. These measures include plans to reduce the proportion of social housing in designated areas through demolition, sale or conversion of existing units. However, these policies have faced criticism and legal challenges for potential discrimination based on ethnic origin. In February 2025, an adviser to the European Union's top court stated that Denmark's housing dispersal policy constitutes direct discrimination, leading to ongoing legal proceedings and debates about the future of such initiatives.¹³

Mixed Cities Fund: The Mixed Cities Fund was created to support affordable social housing and reduce urban segregation, with DKK 10 billion allocated between 2022 and 2035. The fund supports various initiatives, including the construction of new social housing, conversion of commercial properties into residential units and densification projects within existing social housing estates. Additionally, DKK 1.8 billion is allocated for a land purchase loan scheme to help social housing organizations acquire building plots in high-cost areas, facilitating the development of affordable housing in diverse urban settings.¹⁴

Winter Help Package: In response to the rising energy prices and the cost-of-living crisis, Denmark introduced the Winter Help Package to support households, particularly those in social housing, during the winter months. The package included measures like energy price caps to reduce the impact of high heating and electricity costs, along with options for delayed energy payments. Direct financial support was provided to low-income households, ensuring they could manage their utility expenses. This initiative was part of the Danish government's efforts to protect vulnerable groups and maintain housing affordability, with housing associations actively involved in implementing energy-saving solutions alongside the financial aid.¹⁵

Urban renewal programs continue to play a key role in social housing policy. Since the 1990s, Denmark has prioritized rehabilitation over new construction, focusing on improving existing housing stock rather than expanding it. Government subsidies support the modernization of aging social housing estates, improving energy efficiency, accessibility and overall living conditions. The National Housing Fund (Landsbyggefonden) has been instrumental in financing these refurbishments, helping social housing associations upgrade buildings and infrastructure. In 2020, the government allocated DKK 30 billion for 'green renovations' and the development of new affordable housing, aiming to reduce greenhouse

¹³ Rasmussen, L., & Carlsson, I. Y. (2025, February 13). Denmark's housing dispersal policy is discriminatory, EU court adviser says. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/denmarks-housing-dispersal-policy-is-discriminatory-eu-court-adviser-says-2025-02-13/>

¹⁴ Feantsa. (2024). Homelessness strategy Denmark (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.feantsa.org/public/user/epoch/National-Strategies/Homelessness-Strategy-Denmark-Original2024.pdf>

¹⁵ Ritzau/The Local. (2022, September 23). *Denmark announces new winter aid package for households*. The Local Denmark. <https://www.thelocal.dk/20220923/denmark-announces-new-winter-aid-package-for-households>

gas emissions by 70% by 2030 and achieve climate neutrality by 2050.¹⁶ These efforts include the use of sustainable building materials, energy-efficient designs and the incorporation of renewable energy sources in social housing projects.

7.1.3. Challenges

Denmark's social housing sector faces several challenges despite its strong framework for affordability, sustainability and social inclusion. Some of the key issues include:

- **Shortage of Affordable Housing:** While Denmark has a well-developed social housing system, demand for affordable housing in urban areas, especially in cities like Copenhagen and Aarhus, remains high. Long waiting lists for social housing make many low-income residents and young people look for other rental options, which are often expensive.
- **Financial Pressures and Renovation Costs:** Many social housing units require modernization to meet current energy efficiency and sustainability standards. Although the National Building Fund (Landsbyggefonden) provides financial support, large-scale renovations and green retrofitting projects remain expensive and can lead to rent increases, making housing less accessible to vulnerable groups.
- **Gentrification and Market Pressures:** As cities develop, old working-class neighbourhoods with social housing are often chosen for redevelopment. This leads to higher property values and raises concerns about the displacement of lower-income residents. Some social housing areas are being converted into private housing, reducing the availability of public rental homes.
- **"Ghetto" Policies and Social Integration Issues:** Denmark has implemented controversial policies aimed at reducing the number of "parallel societies" in social housing areas with high concentrations of non-Western immigrants. The Parallel Society Act (formerly known as the "Ghetto Law") introduces stricter rules for residents, including the demolition or sale of social housing units and mandatory kindergarten attendance for children in affected areas. While the goal is to enhance social integration, critics argue that these policies lead to discrimination and displacement of marginalized communities.
- **Aging Population and Changing Demographics:** Denmark's aging population presents new challenges for social housing. There is an increasing demand for housing that is accessible and suitable for seniors, as well as better integration of elderly care into the social housing system. Additionally, changes in population and

¹⁶ Housing Europe. (2020, May 12). *Green recovery for Denmark: a new renovation scheme for the social housing sector - Housing Europe*. Housing Europe. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/green-recovery-for-denmark-a-new-renovation-scheme-for-the-social-housing-sector/>

immigration create a need for housing solutions that meet the needs of different household types and cultures.

- **Homelessness and Vulnerable Groups:** Despite Denmark's Housing First approach, homelessness remains a challenge, particularly for individuals with complex needs, such as mental health issues or substance abuse. In some areas, there is still not enough permanent supportive housing, which reduces the effectiveness of homelessness prevention efforts.

7.1.4. Funding Sources and Initiatives

National Programs and Initiatives: Denmark's social housing renovations are largely financed through Landsbyggefonden (National Building Fund), a revolving fund fuelled by tenant contributions. In 2020, a broad political agreement allowed the release of DKK 30.2 billion (€4.1 billion) from this fund for green renovations in public housing over 2020–2026. This investment targets energy efficiency upgrades for 72,000 public housing units by 2026, reducing CO₂ emissions by an estimated 47,000 tonnes. Landsbyggefonden effectively serves as a long-term financing mechanism: tenants pay into the fund via rent, and periodic political agreements set renovation budgets. Annual allocations have supported measures like insulation, efficient heating, and modernization of aging estates. For example, DKK 18.1 billion was spent in 2015–2020 on social housing upgrades (including ~DKK 350 million per year on energy-saving measures). This stable funding model ensures continuous improvements without needing direct yearly state subsidy. In addition, Denmark's National Energy and Climate Plan and Recovery Plan include smaller schemes for building efficiency: e.g. a DKK 315 million (€42 million) subsidy for energy savings in public buildings (focusing on worst-performing municipal buildings). The Recovery Plan also allocates about €65 million for energy retrofits (insulation, heat pump conversions, etc.) in homes and public buildings by 2026. Overall, Denmark's policy framework ("The Road to Energy-Efficient Buildings") encompasses 21 initiatives to cut building energy use 35% by 2050, aligning with EU climate directives.

EU and Other Funding: As a high-income country, Denmark makes limited use of EU grants for social housing energy renovation. However, it participates in EU research and innovation projects and leverages the EU Emissions Trading revenues and national climate funds for green building initiatives. For instance, the Climate Agreement for Energy and Industry dedicates DKK 22.5 billion (€3.0 billion) toward green transition measures by 2030, which can include building efficiency incentives. Denmark's Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP), though relatively small, reinforces building renovations (targeting thousands of private home retrofits and improvements in municipal buildings). Additionally, Danish cities have accessed programs like ELENA (European Local Energy Assistance) for technical assistance on energy retrofit projects, and housing organizations can apply for EU funding

calls under the Horizon Europe “Renovation Wave” for innovative retrofitting approaches. The European Investment Bank has noted Denmark’s strong social housing investment model, but EIB direct financing is less common in Denmark’s case due to ample domestic funding.

Private Sector Involvement: Denmark’s social housing finance is predominantly a solidarity-based public/non-profit system, so traditional public-private partnerships are not widely used for renovations. Construction work is contracted to private firms, but the capital comes mainly from Landsbyggefonden and low-interest loans guaranteed by the government. New social housing construction in Denmark is typically financed by 88% mortgage loans (through private credit institutions with municipal guarantees) and 10% municipal co-financing, with 2% tenant downpayment— a model that shares risk between public and private sectors. For renovations, private mortgage lenders may provide loans backed by Landsbyggefonden’s guarantees. Denmark’s push for sustainability is also attracting private philanthropic funds (like Realdania) and pension funds to co-invest in climate-friendly affordable housing. While explicit PPP schemes are rare, Denmark’s approach can be seen as a public-private hybrid, since tenant-paid funds and private loans (regulated by public agreements) work together to finance upgrades. This model has been praised as a “proven model for long-term social housing investment” in Europe, ensuring that tenants’ savings are reinvested in their homes. Large-scale urban regeneration projects (e.g. the rebuilding of troubled estates under the “Ghetto Plan”) also blend state grants with Landsbyggefonden money and private contractors’ involvement.

Financial Mechanisms: Key funding mechanisms in Denmark include direct subsidies/grants (via Landsbyggefonden) and low-interest loans (often government-backed). Tax incentives play a minimal role – Denmark does not offer homeowner tax credits for energy retrofits in social housing, instead preferring direct investment. The advantage is that needed renovations aren’t dependent on individual tax capacity, ensuring equitable improvements. Tenants benefit from upgrades without huge rent hikes, as costs are pooled sector-wide. By advancing €4 billion in renovations during 2020–2021 as part of a COVID-19 green recovery, Denmark also stimulated the construction sector and created jobs. In summary, Denmark’s funding for energy-efficient renovation of social housing is characterized by long-term pooled funding, political commitment to green upgrades, and integration of social objectives (e.g. accessibility improvements are funded alongside energy measures). This comprehensive approach has enabled deep renovations (new windows, insulation, efficient heating systems, etc.) across tens of thousands of non-profit housing units, markedly improving energy performance and living conditions.

7.1.5. Herning's City-Level Social Housing Developments

Herning, a city in Denmark's Midtjylland region, has been actively engaged in enhancing its social housing landscape through several notable projects and initiatives.

- **Porshøj Neighborhood:** A large renovation project is underway in the Porshøj area in collaboration with the municipal housing company FællesBo. The project covers 21 apartment buildings with a total of 441 apartments. The renovations include installing new bathrooms, kitchens, and energy-efficient systems to create more modern and comfortable homes. The project started in late 2023 and is expected to be completed by summer 2027.¹⁷
- **Mindeparken Area:** Another significant endeavor with FællesBo focuses on the Mindeparken residential area. This includes upgrading 210 apartments across six residential blocks originally constructed in 1956. The renovations include updating technical installations to enhance indoor climate, as well as remodeling certain units to improve accessibility.¹⁸
- **Development of the Herning+ District:** The city is transforming the former hospital grounds into a new district known as Herning+. This area will include a variety of housing types, including social (subsidized) and private dwellings, townhouses, high-rise buildings and associated amenities such as parking facilities, retail outlets, and cafés.¹⁹
- **Fruehøjgaard Housing Association:** This association is an important part of Herning's social housing sector, managing various housing departments for different groups, including families, seniors, and students.

7.2. Italy

Italy's social housing sector, known as Edilizia Residenziale Pubblica (ERP), accounts for approximately 3.5% of the total housing stock. This includes around 900,000 units managed by public housing companies and municipalities, providing affordable rental housing for low-income and vulnerable populations.²⁰ The system operates mainly at regional and municipal levels, ensuring subsidized housing for those in financial need.

¹⁷ NCC to refurbish 441 apartments in Denmark - Inderes. (2023). <https://www.inderes.dk/releases/ncc-to-refurbish-441-apartments-in-denmark>

¹⁸ NCC to refurbish 210 apartments in Herning - Inderes. (2024). <https://www.inderes.fi/releases/ncc-to-refurbish-210-apartments-in-herning>

¹⁹ *Herning + Townhouses*. (2018). Sweco Denmark. <https://www.sweco.dk/en/showroom/herning-townhouses/>

²⁰ The State of the Housing in Europe 2023 [Review of The State of the Housing in Europe 2023]. (2023). Housing Europe's Observatory, 70. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1825/the-state-of-the-housing-in-europe-2023>

Italy's social housing sector is supported by a network of key organizations that play a crucial role in the planning, development, and management of affordable housing. Federcasa, a national association, brings together 144 public housing companies and entities at the provincial, municipal, and regional levels. It oversees approximately 850,000 social housing units, ensuring access to affordable homes for low-income households. Alongside public housing efforts, the Alliance of Italian Cooperatives in the Housing Sector represents the country's cooperative housing movement, uniting 4,700 cooperatives with around 550,000 members. These cooperatives contribute to the creation of accessible housing solutions, often operating on principles of mutual aid and shared ownership. Additionally, Fondazione Housing Sociale (FHS), a private non-profit organization, focuses on developing innovative approaches to financing, constructing, and managing social housing projects. FHS promotes sustainable and community-oriented housing models that go beyond traditional public-sector initiatives. Together, these organizations shape Italy's social housing landscape, balancing public and cooperative efforts with new financial and operational strategies to address the country's growing demand for affordable housing.²¹

7.2.1. Historical Background

The historical development of social housing in Italy has been shaped by economic shifts, political changes and evolving social needs. Social housing in Italy traces its origins to the late 19th and early 20th centuries when industrialization led to rapid urbanization and a growing demand for affordable housing for workers. In response, the government initiated housing projects for low-income families, often through cooperatives. The history of social housing in Italy begins in the early 20th century with the introduction of Law 251/1903, known as the Luzzati Law. Proposed by MP Luzzati, it created financial entities and cooperatives responsible for building and renting or selling housing to those in need, primarily targeting the working class. The law established the Istituto Autonomo per le Case Popolari (IACP-Independent Institution for Tenement Building) in 1908, which played a major role in social housing for many decades. The aim was to provide housing to the lower classes.

During the Fascist era (1922–1943), the government built large public housing projects to improve living conditions while maintaining control over urban development. After World War II, Italy faced a severe housing crisis due to wartime destruction and mass rural-to-urban migration. To address this, the government launched large-scale social housing programs, most notably the INA-Casa Plan (1949–1963), which aimed to provide housing for workers and improve urban infrastructure. This initiative led to the construction of large social housing estates, shaping the urban landscape of many Italian cities.

²¹ The State of the Housing in Europe 2023 [Review of The State of the Housing in Europe 2023]. (2023). Housing Europe's Observatory, 70. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1825/the-state-of-the-housing-in-europe-2023>

In the 1960s and 1970s, further legislative reforms, such as Law No. 865/1971, redefined public housing by emphasizing social needs over speculative construction and decentralizing housing responsibilities to regional and local governments. This period also saw an increase in the construction of public housing.

However, from the 1980s onward, economic crises and shifting political priorities led to a decline in public investment in social housing. The government moved away from mass construction toward rehabilitation and urban renewal projects. Privatization and partnerships between the government and private companies became more common and social housing started to include a mix of different income groups and focus more on sustainability.

7.2.2. Recent Policies and Development

Recent policies and developments in Italy's social housing sector reflect ongoing efforts to address housing shortages, improve living conditions and promote sustainability. The Italian government has introduced several measures in response to housing affordability and urban regeneration challenges, with a focus on both new construction and the revitalization of existing housing stock.

National Housing Plan (Piano Nazionale per l'Housing): This initiative aims to increase the availability of public housing and improve living conditions by promoting the construction and renovation of affordable housing. It allocates resources to municipal governments and public entities to support the development of new housing projects and the renovation of existing social housing. The plan is designed to facilitate the social inclusion of low-income households by providing affordable, energy-efficient homes.

Urban Regeneration Program (Programma di Rigenerazione Urbana): This program encourages the transformation of neglected urban areas into vibrant, sustainable communities. This program prioritizes the redevelopment of old public housing complexes, integrating them with new, mixed-use developments that include affordable housing, public spaces and local services. It emphasizes improving the quality of life in urban spaces through the integration of housing, public spaces and local services.

7.2.3. Challenges

Despite ongoing efforts to improve social housing in Italy, several challenges persist, limiting access and quality. Key issues include housing shortages, outdated infrastructure, bureaucratic hurdles and rising costs.

- **Housing Shortage and Rising Demand:** There is a growing demand for affordable housing, particularly in major cities like Milan, Rome, and Bologna, where rent prices have risen significantly. However, the availability of social housing remains

insufficient to meet the needs of low-income households, young people and vulnerable groups.

- **Aging and Poorly Maintained Housing Stock:** A significant portion of Italy's social housing was built decades ago and now requires urgent renovation. Many buildings have poor energy efficiency, outdated infrastructure, and unsuitable living conditions.
- **Bureaucratic and Administrative Barriers:** Complex administrative procedures and regional differences in social housing policies create inefficiencies in project implementation.
- **Social Segregation and Gentrification:** Many social housing estates are in outer or less-developed areas, which can lead to social isolation and limited access to services, jobs, and public transport. At the same time, rising housing costs in city centers are forcing lower-income residents to move to suburban areas with fewer resources, increasing the need for affordable housing.
- **Rising Construction and Renovation Costs:** The increasing costs of construction materials, labor shortages and inflation have made it more difficult to build new social housing units and renovate existing ones. Limited availability of affordable land in urban areas further complicates new housing developments.

7.2.4. Funding Sources and Initiatives

National Government Programs: Italy has employed a mix of generous tax incentives, dedicated funds, and grant programs to boost energy efficiency in residential and social housing:

- **“Superbonus 110%” Tax Incentive (2020–2023):** To accelerate renovations, Italy introduced the Superbonus scheme, allowing homeowners (including housing associations) to claim 110% tax deduction on expenses for energy efficiency and seismic upgrades²². This effectively made deep renovations free (and even profitable) for participants, as the tax credit could be transferred or sold to banks and contractors for upfront cash²³. The Superbonus, backed by €13.95 billion from Italy's RRP (Recovery Plan), led to a surge of building upgrades and economic activity. By 2023, it helped renovate over 100,000 buildings. However, its cost far exceeded expectations (an estimated €150 billion in credits in four years, versus €35 billion projected), straining public finances. In 2023–24 the government reformed the program: credit trading was curtailed, and the subsidy rate is being reduced. Starting 2025, Italy will phase down to pre-2020 incentive levels, ending the 110% superbonus. Under the 2025 Budget Law, standard home renovation deductions will be 50% for primary residences (down from 65% for eco-bonus measures previously)

²² [Italy's recovery and resilience – Supported projects: Nation-wide investments - European Commission](#)

²³ [Italy curbs costly incentives for home improvements | Reuters](#)

and 36% for second homes. Generous support for fossil-fuel heating replacements is being eliminated – from 2025, installing a gas-only boiler will no longer qualify for bonuses (the state will only support hybrid or renewable systems). These changes aim to make incentives fiscally sustainable while still encouraging efficiency in principle, albeit with more modest benefits.

- National Energy Efficiency Fund & Conto Termico: Alongside tax credits, Italy operates the National Fund for Energy Efficiency (FNEE) which provides guarantees and soft loans for energy renovation projects (including public buildings and social housing). The RRP calls for strengthening this fund and dedicating an extra €6 billion to energy efficiency in municipalities²⁴. Additionally, the “Conto Termico” incentive scheme managed by GSE offers direct grants (rebates) to public bodies and others for smaller-scale efficiency works (e.g. insulation, efficient boilers, solar thermal) – up to 65% of costs, which social housing entities (often publicly owned) can tap into. These instruments, while smaller than Superbonus, continue to provide ongoing support for upgrades.
- Housing Quality and Social Housing Programs: Italy’s government has targeted social housing through specific investment programs. The PINQuA – National Innovative Program for Housing Quality (launched in 2019) was reinforced under the RRP with €2.8 billion. PINQuA funds regeneration of public housing and deprived areas, aiming to build new social housing and retrofit existing stock with green and modern standards. Projects funded under PINQuA emphasize sustainability and inclusion (e.g. energy-efficient refurbishments, creation of affordable units for vulnerable groups). By 2026, this is expected to significantly modernize Italy’s social housing stock and add new nearly-zero-energy homes. Another RRP measure allocates €0.96 billion for student housing (which intersects with affordable housing goals).
- Planned 2025+ Incentives (“Bonus Case Popolari”): Recognizing the need to focus on low-income households after Superbonus, Italy’s 2024 budget introduced a new “Bonus Case Popolari” (Public Housing Bonus) program with €1.38 billion earmarked for 2025–2026²⁵. This initiative is designed to combat energy poverty by funding energy renovations in:
 - Public residential buildings owned by municipalities or public entities (ERP housing),
 - Social housing managed by cooperatives or social enterprises,
 - Privately-owned apartment buildings where low-income families reside. To receive funding, projects must achieve at least 30% reduction in energy needs.

²⁴<https://www.housingeurope.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2024/12/Recovery%20and%20Resilience%20Plan%20in%20Italy.pdf>

The program will be implemented by GSE (the Energy Services Operator) in coordination with the finance ministry. Details will be set by decree, but the scheme will likely provide a mix of grants and concessional loans to municipalities and housing providers. Notably, it is structured to leverage public-private partnerships, with ESCOs (Energy Service Companies) expected to co-finance and execute the renovations. Financial partners include SACE (Italy's export-credit agency) and Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP), indicating a blend of public investment and private capital. This targeted program marks a shift to a more calibrated incentive, focusing on vulnerable communities and social housing rather than broad-based tax breaks. It complements other ongoing measures like tax deductions (now reduced) and aligns with EU priorities to alleviate energy poverty.

EU-Level Funding and Support in Italy: Italy has been one of the largest beneficiaries of EU funding for building renovations:

- Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF): Italy's RRF devoted €16.9 billion to energy efficiency in buildings²⁶— by far the biggest allocation in Europe. This included funding the Superbonus scheme (nearly €14 billion from EU grants) and investments in social housing and urban renewal (PINQuA, etc.). These EU funds essentially subsidized a huge wave of private building upgrades and public housing improvements between 2021–2026. By end of 2025, the RRF target is at least 32 million m² of buildings upgraded via Superbonus and other measures.
- European Structural and Investment Funds: Italy also uses European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) money for energy efficiency at regional levels. Several regional operational programs (2014–2020 and 2021–2027 cycles) fund housing rehab, especially in Southern Italy. For example, ERDF has co-financed upgrades in public housing estates (insulation, solar panels, efficient lighting) in cities like Naples and Palermo under urban development projects. The 2021–27 cohesion policy earmarks funds for integrated urban plans and sustainable social housing (in line with PINQuA's goals). These grants often require meeting EU energy standards (like improving buildings to at least energy class B).
- Horizon Europe and ELENA: Italian cities and housing providers are active in EU innovation programs. Projects such as EU Horizon 2020 “RENAISSANCE” and “EURHONET” pilots have demonstrated deep renovation in social housing with EU research funds. In addition, some municipalities have tapped the ELENA facility (European Commission/EIB program) for technical assistance to prepare large-scale retrofit projects – a notable example is Milan, which received ELENA support to

²⁶ [Italy's recovery and resilience plan - European Commission](#)

structure energy performance contracts for public buildings (including social housing blocks).

- EU Energy Efficiency Fund (EEEF) and InvestEU: Italy has drawn on financing instruments like the EEEF, which provided loans for retrofit projects in cities (e.g. street lighting and public building insulation in Ferrara). Under InvestEU (2021–2027), Italy can access guarantees and loans for green housing – for instance, the InvestEU Advisory Hub is helping design an affordable housing investment blueprint in Italy²⁷. The European Investment Bank (EIB) is a crucial partner: it has financed over €6.5 billion in social and affordable housing projects across Europe in the last five years, including Italy. In 2023 the EIB provided a €34 million loan to a social housing fund in Milan to rebuild 200 apartments to high energy efficiency standards, its first direct investment with a real-estate social housing fund. This demonstrates how EU-level financing is blended into Italian initiatives, often via loans to CDP or private funds that amplify public resources.

Private Sector Involvement: The scale of Italy’s renovation drive has necessitated extensive private sector involvement:

- Tax Credit Market: The Superbonus scheme effectively turned construction companies and banks into financing partners. Homeowners could assign their 110% tax credit to contractors as payment, and contractors in turn sold credits to banks or investors²⁸<https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/italy-curbs-costly-incentives-home-improvements-2024-03-26/>. This created a large public-private market for energy retrofit financing, mobilizing private capital (banks) to front the costs in exchange for state-backed credits. While this boosted participation, it also revealed risks – fraud and ballooning fiscal cost – leading to stricter controls and, ultimately, the winding down of credit trading by 2024.
- Energy Service Companies (ESCOs): Italy has a mature ESCO market due to its White Certificates scheme and energy savings obligations. ESCOs have undertaken performance-based retrofits in public housing by covering upfront costs and sharing the savings. For example, some municipalities contract ESCOs to upgrade heating systems in social flats, repaid via lower utility bills. The new Bonus Case Popolari explicitly plans to involve ESCOs as co-investors and project managers <https://www.rinnovabili.it/green-building/building/efficientamento-edilizia-pubblica-dalla-manovra-138-mld/>, illustrating a PPP model: public grants will improve project viability, while private ESCO financing and expertise maximize the reach of funds. This approach aims to attract private co-financing to supplement the €1.38 billion public investment, increasing the number of homes renovated.

²⁷ [Italy: Social Housing - EIB and Investire SGR sign €34 million loan to build more than 200 housing units in the centre of Milan](#)

²⁸ [Italy curbs costly incentives for home improvements | Reuters](#)

- **Public-Private Funds for Social Housing:** Even before the current initiatives, Italy pioneered PPPs in social housing through FIA (Fondo Investimenti per l’Abitare) – a national fund managed by CDP that pools public and private investors (banks, foundations, cooperatives) to develop affordable housing. Organizations like Fondazione Housing Sociale (FHS) facilitate these partnerships, blending resources for new construction and rehabilitation. Such funds have financed energy-efficient social housing projects (e.g. nearly-zero-energy buildings for affordable rental in Turin) and continue to operate alongside government programs. The EIB-backed Ca’ Granda fund in Milan is one recent example, involving a hospital foundation, CDP, and a bank-managed real estate fund to deliver efficient homes for moderate-income families.
- **Green Bonds and Private Loans:** Some larger Italian regions and housing companies have issued green bonds to raise capital for renovation. For instance, Lombardy floated bonds to fund energy retrofits in public buildings, and Milan is exploring sustainable bonds for housing upgrades. Private banks in Italy also offer eco-loans at reduced rates for homeowners doing energy-saving works, often encouraged by state guarantee schemes. ALTROConsumo (a consumer association) and some cooperative banks have partnered to provide low-interest loans to condo associations planning insulation or solar panel installations, complementing state incentives.

Financial Mechanisms Used: Italy’s toolkit covers tax incentives, grants, low-interest loans, and guarantees:

- **Tax incentives:** Historically crucial (Ecobonus, Superbonus), now being scaled back to more normal levels but still available for many households. These directly reduce renovation costs via tax savings.
- **Grants and subsidies:** Provided through programs like PINQuA and the new social housing bonus, as well as regional EU-funded grants. These do not require repayment and target public entities or specific social outcomes.
- **Low-interest loans:** Often supported by CDP or guaranteed by the state (e.g. **“Sismabonus” credit guarantees for seismic upgrades, which often pair with energy retrofits*). ALTIM, Italy’s development bank, offers subsidized loans for energy efficiency to public building owners. The new social housing scheme will likely use soft loans in combination with grants.
- **Municipal incentives:** Some cities waive or reduce local taxes (like property tax or building permit fees) for projects that achieve high energy standards. For example, Milan provided an extra volumetric bonus (allowing an extra floor) to developers who commit to Class A energy performance in refurbishments.
- **Private finance and co-funding:** As noted, Italy leverages private funds via credit trading (previously) and now via ESCO investment and bank loans. The blending of grants with private loans is increasingly favored to stretch public money further – an

approach encouraged by the EU. For instance, the EU's PF4EE program (Private Finance for Energy Efficiency) has operated in Italy to provide risk sharing for banks lending to efficiency projects.

7.2.5. Trieste's City-Level Social Housing Developments

Trieste, a historic port city located in northeastern Italy, is known for its strategic position on the Adriatic Sea and its rich cultural heritage. Trieste has implemented several initiatives to enhance its social housing sector, focusing on accessibility, community integration, and support for vulnerable populations.

- **ATER Trieste's Initiatives:** The Territorial Agency for Residential Housing (ATER) plays a key role in managing and developing social housing in Trieste. One significant project is the redevelopment of Casa Capon, which added three new housing units specifically designed for individuals with disabilities and single-parent families. These apartments are part of a broader effort by the municipal administration to provide suitable, affordable housing for vulnerable groups.²⁹
- **Habitat MicroAree Program:** This program represents a collaborative approach integrating social, health, and housing policies. This initiative aims to improve living conditions by fostering community involvement and strengthening social cohesion. By actively engaging residents in the development and maintenance of their neighborhoods, the program seeks to create supportive environments that enhance the quality of life for all inhabitants.³⁰
- **Housing First Trieste:** Addressing homelessness through innovative strategies, the Housing First Trieste initiative provides permanent housing accompanied by intensive social support. In 2019, the program offered 10 apartments to 30 residents and assisted five families in achieving housing independence. This approach prioritizes immediate housing solutions without preconditions, facilitating a stable environment that enables individuals to rebuild their lives.³¹
- **Policy Reforms in Friuli Venezia Giulia Region:** The Friuli Venezia Giulia region, which includes Trieste, is undertaking comprehensive reforms to enhance housing policies. These reforms aim to improve efficiency and expand support for vulnerable populations. The region has allocated €70 million to incentivize private photovoltaic

²⁹ Editorial. (2024, October 16). *Trieste Expands Accessible Housing with Redevelopment of Casa Capon - InTrieste*. InTrieste. <https://www.intrieste.com/2024/10/17/trieste-expands-accessible-housing-with-redevelopment-of-casa-capon>

³⁰ *Habitat Microaree in Trieste – A Caring City*: Transform. (2021). Transform-Integratedcommunitycare.com. <https://transform-integratedcommunitycare.com/casestudy/habitat-microaree-a-caring-city/>

³¹ *How an Italian finds a home in Trieste after eight years living on the streets of Rome | European Social Fund Plus*. (2025, February 28). Europa.eu. <https://european-social-fund-plus.ec.europa.eu/en/projects/housing-first-italy>

system installations and €25 million for social housing and early childhood development programs.³²

7.3. Latvia

Social housing in Latvia is a crucial aspect of the country's social welfare system, aimed at providing affordable and adequate housing for low-income households, the elderly and other vulnerable groups. Latvia gained independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, the housing sector went through significant changes. The privatization of housing led to a more market-driven system, but it also created challenges for people who struggle to find affordable housing, especially in large cities like Riga. Social housing remains a key solution to ensure that everyone has access to suitable living conditions.

A large part of Latvia's social housing stock consists of old Soviet-era apartment blocks, known as Khrushchyovkas and Brezhnevkas. These buildings, constructed rapidly during the Soviet era, are now in poor condition and require expensive renovations to meet modern energy efficiency and quality of life standards.³³ Recent data compiled by Eurostat highlights the housing challenges in Latvia. The country ranks among the top 10 EU nations facing housing issues, with significant proportions of its population living in substandard conditions. In fact, Latvia ranks fifth in the EU for problems like leaking roofs, with over 19% of households experiencing this issue in 2019. This emphasizes the ongoing difficulties in maintaining and upgrading Latvia's housing stock, particularly in the context of aging Soviet-era buildings.³⁴

Key organizations involved in managing and improving social housing in Latvia include the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development (VARAM), which sets housing policies, and local municipalities, which are responsible for managing most of the social housing stock. The State Housing Development Agency (VHDA) also plays an important role by supporting housing projects and providing financial assistance.

7.3.1. Historical Background

The development of social housing in Latvia has been shaped by historical, political and economic transformations. These changes, from the early 20th century to the present, have influenced housing policies, affordability and accessibility for vulnerable groups.

³² Editorial. (2024, December 13). *Friuli Venezia Giulia Unveils Ambitious Housing and Infrastructure Plans for 2025* - InTrieste. <https://www.intrieste.com/2024/12/13/friuli-venezia-giulia-unveils-ambitious-housing-and-infrastructure-plans-for-2025/>

³³ Wikipedia. (2023, January 19). *Khrushchevka*. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Khrushchevka>

³⁴ Inguna Ukenābele. (2021). *Soviet buildings major cause of collapse in Latvian housing quality*. Eng.lsm.lv; LSM. <https://eng.lsm.lv/article/society/environment/soviet-buildings-major-cause-of-collapse-in-latvian-housing-quality.a391113/>

Before Latvia's incorporation into the Soviet Union, housing was primarily a private sector responsibility. The country had a mix of urban and rural housing, with wealthier individuals owning private properties and lower-income groups relying on rented housing. Social housing in the modern sense was almost non-existent, as the state played a minimal role in providing affordable housing solutions.

During the Soviet era, housing policies shifted dramatically. The state took full control over housing, nationalizing private properties and implementing a centrally planned system. Large-scale housing projects were undertaken to accommodate urban workers, leading to the construction of mass-produced apartment blocks (such as Khrushchyovkas and Brezhnevkas) in major cities like Riga. While these developments significantly increased housing availability, they often lacked quality and energy efficiency. Social housing was provided as part of state employment, with workers and their families allocated apartments based on occupation and status. However, waiting lists were long, and housing shortages persisted.

Following Latvia's independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, the housing sector underwent radical changes. The state gradually withdrew from housing provision, leading to large-scale privatization of previously state-owned apartments. By the late 1990s, over 80% of housing had been privatized, transferring responsibility for maintenance and renovation to individual owners. However, this rapid privatization created challenges, particularly for low-income households that struggled with rising costs, inadequate housing conditions, and a lack of state support. Unlike in some other post-Soviet countries, Latvia did not establish a large-scale, state-funded social housing sector. Instead, municipalities were tasked with managing social housing programs, but limited resources and funding led to insufficient social housing stock.

In the 2000s and beyond, Latvia has attempted to address social housing issues through various policy measures. Municipalities provide rental housing for low-income households, but the availability remains limited. Many Soviet-era buildings require urgent renovation, but funding constraints make large-scale improvements difficult.

7.3.2. Recent Policies and Development

Riga is one of the 112 cities selected to participate in the EU Mission for 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030, also known as the NetZeroCities initiative. As a Mission City, Riga is committed to accelerating its transition towards climate neutrality by implementing innovative solutions. This mission supports the city's efforts to develop policies and projects that reduce carbon emissions, enhance urban resilience, and improve the overall quality of life for residents. Riga's participation aligns with broader European sustainability goals, positioning the city as a leader in climate action within Latvia.

In recent years, Latvia has undertaken several initiatives to enhance social housing and address housing affordability challenges.

Housing Availability Guidelines (2023–2027): Approved by the Cabinet of Ministers on November 7, 2023, these guidelines aim to improve housing accessibility for various income levels. They focus on supporting vulnerable groups, increasing the supply of affordable rental housing, stimulating new housing construction and investing in the renovation of existing housing stock. The guidelines also propose developing a new law to replace the existing "Assistance in Housing Matters" law, ensuring better support for disadvantaged individuals and allowing assistance across municipalities to promote labor mobility.³⁵

Collaboration with the European Investment Bank (EIB): In October 2024, the Latvian government partnered with the EIB to expand affordable rental housing. The EIB's Advisory Services are assisting in creating a blueprint for financing, procurement, and pilot project development. The initial phase aims to construct up to 2,260 affordable rental apartments nationwide by 2030, targeting professionals such as teachers, medics, and police officers.³⁶

Affordable Rental Housing Projects: As of December 2024, construction has commenced on six affordable rental housing projects in cities including Valmiera, Bauska, Jelgava, Tukums, and Ventspils, resulting in over 420 new apartments. Supported by the Development Finance Institution ALTUM and co-financed by the European Union Recovery Fund, these projects aim to provide quality, energy-efficient housing with rents not exceeding €6.39 per square meter.³⁷

Public-Private Partnership Initiatives: In October 2024, the Latvian government, in collaboration with the European Investment Bank (EIB), launched a public-private partnership program titled "Rental Housing for Latvian Professionals." This initiative aims to construct up to 2,266 affordable rental apartments by 2030, targeting professionals such as teachers, medics, firefighters, police officers, and military personnel. The program involves 13 municipalities, including Riga. Municipalities have committed to providing suitable land for construction and co-financing the projects to ensure affordability for residents.³⁸

³⁵ *Approved Housing Availability Guidelines until 2027*. (2025). Em.gov.lv. <https://www.em.gov.lv/en/article/approved-housing-availability-guidelines-until-2027>

³⁶ EIB. (2024, October 2). *Latvia: EIB and Latvian government to collaborate on affordable rental housing*. European Investment Bank. <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2024-357-eib-and-latvian-government-to-collaborate-on-affordable-rental-housing>

³⁷ *Six Affordable Rental Housing Projects Being Built Across Latvia with ALTUM Support*. (2025). Em.gov.lv. <https://www.em.gov.lv/en/article/six-affordable-rental-housing-projects-being-built-across-latvia-altum-support>

³⁸ *Plans to build up to 2266 rental housing units for professionals in sectors of national and regional importance in Latvia by 2030*. (2024). Wwww.vni.lv. <https://www.vni.lv/en/news/plans-to-build-up-to-2266-rental-housing-units-for-professionals-in-sectors-of-national-and-regional-importance-in-latvia-by-2030>

7.3.3. Challenges

Social housing in Latvia faces several challenges, which are related to both historical factors and current economic, social, and political contexts. These challenges are affecting the availability, affordability, and quality of housing for vulnerable groups.

- **Limited Housing Stock:** Latvia's social housing sector suffers from a limited stock of available units, particularly for low-income and vulnerable populations. The construction of new social housing units has been slow, and many existing units are outdated, requiring significant investment for renovation and modernization. As a result, there is an ongoing shortage of affordable housing for those in need.
- **Aging Housing Stock:** Many of Latvia's social housing units are part of the Soviet-era housing legacy (such as the Khrushchyovkas) that were poorly constructed and are now in bad condition. These buildings have poor energy efficiency and require costly renovations.
- **Affordability Issues:** Despite improvements in housing policies, the affordability of social housing remains a key challenge. Although rents are regulated, they still tend to be unaffordable for low-income individuals and families, especially those living in rural areas or with limited access to social services. Furthermore, there is an increasing gap between incomes and housing costs, particularly in urban areas like Riga.
- **Geographical Disparities:** There are significant regional disparities in the availability of social housing, particularly between urban and rural areas. While cities like Riga have a relatively higher concentration of social housing, rural areas face greater challenges in providing affordable housing options. This increases migration patterns from rural areas to cities, creating additional pressure on urban housing markets.
- **Rural Depopulation:** Rural areas in Latvia are facing significant depopulation, with many young people migrating to cities for better opportunities. This demographic shift has led to an excess of unoccupied housing in rural areas, but the housing is often of poor quality or lacks basic services. As a result, these areas are left with underutilized housing stock while the demand for affordable housing in cities remains high.
- **Impact of Economic Inequality:** Latvia's income inequality is a significant driver of housing challenges. High poverty rates, especially among certain demographic groups such as elderly individuals and large families, limit the ability to afford quality housing. Economic inequality also affects access to social housing, as people living in poverty are often the most vulnerable and hardest to house.

7.3.4. Funding Sources and Initiatives

National and EU-Supported Programs: Latvia's social and multi-apartment housing stock (much of it Soviet-era buildings) has seen a major push for energy retrofitting in recent years, heavily supported by EU funds and state financial instruments:

- **ERDF-Funded Renovation Program (2016–2023):** Using the European Regional Development Fund, Latvia established the Energy Efficiency Programme for Multi-Apartment Buildings (EEPMB), managed by the state development finance institution ALTUM. This program combined low-interest loans + grants + guarantees to help homeowner associations and municipalities renovate apartment blocks. It supported 624 renovation projects across Latvia³⁹ – typically installing insulation, new windows, efficient heating systems, and other upgrades. A typical financing package covered about 50% of costs as a grant and the rest as a loan to be repaid by apartment owners over up to 20 years, with ALTUM providing state-backed guarantees. By 2020, ALTUM had also secured an €18 million EIB loan (with an EU LIFE program guarantee) to bolster financing for these energy projects⁴⁰ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2020-074-altum-and-eib-join-forces-for-energy-efficiency-investments-in-latvia>.
- **Recovery and Resilience Facility (2021–2026):** Under the EU Recovery Plan (NextGenerationEU), Latvia launched a follow-on renovation support program with RRF resources. This introduced a “capital rebate” model: building associations taking loans for renovation could get 30–50% of the principal written off upon completion, depending on energy savings achieved. For example, a recent project in Lielvārde was completed with 50% of its €443k eligible costs covered by a capital grant⁴¹. As of late 2024, 166 building projects have been approved under the RRF scheme. The RRF has allocated about €57 million in funding for these rebates so far. This co-financing significantly lowers monthly payments for residents – in the Lielvārde case, energy bills per m² dropped almost by half post-renovation thanks to the improvements and subsidy. The RRF program must be completed by autumn 2026, by which time Latvia expects to renovate hundreds more apartment buildings.
- **New EU Structural Funds Program (2024–2029):** To ensure continuity after RRF, Latvia approved a new EU Structural Fund support program in Dec 2024 with €173 million aimed at multi-apartment energy efficiency, running through 2029. This program is designed to further promote the ESCO market in Latvia. It offers a combined loan+grant instrument: building owners take an ALTUM loan or bank loan (possibly guaranteed by ALTUM), and upon achieving ≥30% energy savings, they

³⁹ [Financial instruments and grants combination for energy efficiency of multi-apartment buildings in Latvia](#)

⁴⁰ [ALTUM and EIB join forces for energy efficiency investments in Latvia](#)

⁴¹ [First Multi-Apartment Building Energy Efficiency Renovation Project Completed with ALTUM Support | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

receive a 40% grant (capital rebate) on the loan principal. The grant can increase to 45% if using innovative solutions like ventilated facades, and up to 50% if using prefabricated insulation panels or a “district approach” (three or more buildings refurbishing together). By incentivizing bundled projects and modern methods, Latvia hopes to accelerate renovations and reduce costs through scale. The program simplifies application procedures (accepting simplified energy audits and allowing reservation of rebates early). Importantly, it encourages Energy Service Companies to act as intermediaries or project managers for building groups— an approach to overcome the lack of capacity in some homeowner associations. This new funding (largely ERDF money for 2021–27 period) is expected to renovate ~266 buildings by 2029.⁴²

- **Municipal Social Housing Renovation Program:** In parallel with the broad multi-apartment scheme, Latvia has a targeted program for municipal social housing (often apartments reserved for low-income or vulnerable residents). Approved in 2023, this program provides €60.9 million (ERDF €51.7M + local €9.1M co-finance) for municipalities to renovate or construct social housing units⁴³. It falls under the EU Cohesion Policy goal of social inclusion. Municipalities can get grants to refurbish vacant apartments or buildings they own into decent, energy-efficient social rentals, or to build new ones, on condition that the housing is rented to eligible vulnerable groups (e.g. low-income families, the elderly, disabled persons). By 2029 this aims to create at least 1,865 new or upgraded social housing units across Latvia. At least 1,200 of those are expected from renovation of existing spaces. This program addresses the acute shortage of social housing (fewer than 2% of Latvia’s housing stock) and its poor quality⁴⁴. Upgraded units will meet modern efficiency and habitability standards (insulation, new plumbing/heating, etc.), reducing energy poverty for tenants. The Central Finance and Contracting Agency will run calls for project proposals from municipalities, ensuring funds are spent by 2029. This is a key step as previously municipalities had little funding to maintain or improve social flats.

Private Sector Involvement: Engaging the private sector has been crucial in Latvia, given limited public funds:

- **ALTUM’s Financial Instruments:** ALTUM itself operates like a public-private vehicle – it channels public (EU/state) funds in combination with commercial bank loans. Typically, apartment associations in Latvia secure a loan from a local bank for part of the renovation cost; ALTUM provides a guarantee to reduce the bank’s risk and manages the disbursement of grant subsidies. This way, private banks are lending

⁴² [€173 Million for Multi-Apartment Building Renovation | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

⁴³ [Funding Available for Municipalities for the Renovation and Construction of Social Housing | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

⁴⁴ [Latvia: EIB and Latvian government to collaborate on affordable rental housing](#)

capital into projects backed by EU/public guarantees. The model has worked well: since 2007, over 1,367 buildings were renovated with EU co-financing totaling €279M, leveraging additional private co-financing⁴⁵. The new 2024 program continues this combined approach, effectively a PPP between the government (providing rebates) and banks/ESCOs (providing upfront financing).

- Energy Service Companies (ESCOs): Latvia is promoting ESCO-based renovations where a private company finances and carries out the work, then the residents repay via energy savings. A pioneering example was the SUNSHINE project (EU-funded) in which a Latvian ESCO renovated multi-family buildings and recouped costs from energy bill reductions. The upcoming scheme explicitly allows ESCOs to bundle buildings and secure the 50% rebate for district approaches <https://www.em.gov.lv/en/article/eu173-million-multi-apartment-building-renovation>, making the ESCO model more attractive. This is essentially a public-private partnership: the ESCO invests and guarantees performance; public funds reward the achieved savings, lowering the ESCO's needed recovery from residents.
- International Financial Institutions: The European Investment Bank and European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) have supported Latvia's housing energy upgrades. Beyond the ALTUM loan noted earlier, EBRD helped finance pilot ESCO renovations in Latvian apartments through risk-sharing facilities (e.g. the EBRD credit line for Baltic energy efficiency). Private Finance for Energy Efficiency (PF4EE), an EU instrument, was used in Latvia to enable commercial bank lending for efficiency in SMEs and buildings⁴⁶. Such partnerships bring in private capital with EU guarantees. Moreover, Investors (ESCO funds) from abroad have shown interest in Latvia's renovation program because the grants secure a portion of returns.
- Developers and Construction Sector: The private construction sector in Latvia benefits from these programs, as thousands of contracts for insulation, new windows, ventilation upgrades, etc., are awarded. The government's simplified procedures and pipeline of projects give construction firms confidence to invest in capacity (and even in some cases co-invest in projects). No explicit tax incentives for private landlords exist in Latvia, so direct investment is limited; instead, private real estate developers partner with municipalities on affordable housing PPPs for new construction (e.g. building rentals for key workers with long-term leases to cities, as promoted in a 2024 EIB advisory project)⁴⁷. This indirectly helps energy efficiency by ensuring new builds are built to high standards and old inefficient stock can be retired.

Financial Mechanisms: Latvia's approach relies on grant-loan combinations and guarantees rather than tax breaks:

⁴⁵ [€173 Million for Multi-Apartment Building Renovation | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

⁴⁶ [ALTUM and EIB join forces for energy efficiency investments in Latvia](#)

⁴⁷ [Latvia: EIB and Latvian government to collaborate on affordable rental housing](#)

1. *Capital rebates (grants)*: Cover 30–50% of project costs post-completion, as a reward for energy savings achieved⁴⁸. This directly reduces the repayable loan amount for homeowners.
2. *Soft loans*: Provided via ALTUM or local banks, often fixed low-interest and long-term (up to 20–30 years). For instance, an affordable housing loan program offers municipalities 30-year loans at 0.69% interest for constructing rental housing⁴⁹.
3. *Municipal co-financing*: Some city councils contribute a small share of costs (or offer property tax relief) if a renovation addresses structural safety or heritage preservation along with energy goals.
4. *EU cohesion funds*: As grants administered by ministries for specific targets (e.g. social housing, noted above).
5. *Energy grants for low-income households*: Latvia also uses part of its EU Social Fund and national budget to assist low-income homeowners with co-payments, ensuring they are not left behind in renovation waves (important as many apartment owners are pensioners who might struggle to afford loan payments even with 50% grant – local social assistance bridges that gap in some cases).
6. *Green mortgages*: An emerging mechanism – banks in Latvia have started offering slightly better terms (lower interest or higher loan-to-value) for certified energy-efficient home upgrades or purchases, recognizing reduced utility costs improve repayment ability.

Latvia's strategy shows a clear evolution and continuity of funding: ERDF -> RRF -> new ERDF, with no gaps in support⁵⁰. This long-term commitment is crucial given the large number of outdated buildings. Energy retrofits in Latvia have yielded big efficiency gains (often 50%+ heating energy savings per building) and extended these buildings' lifespans by decades⁵¹. They also contribute to energy poverty reduction and lower Latvia's reliance on imported gas. By 2030, thanks to these programs, thousands of Latvian families will live in renovated, warmer homes, and municipalities will have increased stocks of efficient social housing – all achieved by blending EU solidarity funds with innovative financing models at the local level.

7.3.5. Riga's City-Level Social Housing Developments

Riga, the capital of Latvia, has been actively addressing social housing challenges through various initiatives aimed at increasing the availability of affordable housing and improving living conditions for its residents.

⁴⁸ [€173 Million for Multi-Apartment Building Renovation | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

⁴⁹ [Six Affordable Rental Housing Projects Being Built Across Latvia with ALTUM Support | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

⁵⁰ [Financial instruments and grants combination for energy efficiency of multi-apartment buildings in Latvia](#)

⁵¹ [First Multi-Apartment Building Energy Efficiency Renovation Project Completed with ALTUM Support | Ekonomikas ministrija](#)

- Expansion of Social Housing Units: The Riga Municipality has secured over €10 million in European Union funding to develop 351 new social housing units. This initiative is projected to reduce the housing waiting list by approximately 18-20%, significantly improving access for vulnerable populations.⁵²
- Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): To further address the housing shortage, Riga is exploring public-private partnerships to develop energy-efficient, affordable apartments. The plan aims to construct 2,260 such units across Latvia by 2030, with 1,000 units designated for Riga. This project employs a public-private partnership model, where municipalities provide land and co-finance rental subsidies, while private investors contribute to the development, ensuring energy-efficient and affordable housing solutions.⁵³
- Integration of Health and Social Services: The Riga City Council's Welfare Department has led the creation of integrated social housing complexes that combine health and social services. This approach aims to provide comprehensive support to residents, particularly the elderly and those with special needs, enhancing their quality of life and promoting social inclusion.

⁵² English, L. (2024). *Riga gets EU funding for social housing*. Eng.lsm.lv; LSM.

<https://eng.lsm.lv/article/economy/economy/09.08.2024-riga-gets-eu-funding-for-social-housing.a564473/>

⁵³ Fingar, C. (2025, March 4). *Riga eyes public-private partnerships to unlock development potential - Real Asset Insight*. Real Asset Insight. <https://realassetinsight.com/thought-leader/riga-eyes-public-private-partnerships-to-unlock-development-potential/>

8. Conclusion

This policy review highlights the diverse landscape of social housing across SUPERSHINE's fellow and lighthouse cities. It provides a comprehensive analysis of social housing policies and developments across Europe, aligning with the broader EU targets for sustainability, affordability and inclusivity. It examines the socio-economic structures and retrofit policies of fellow cities, highlighting their approaches to improving social housing conditions. Additionally, the report explores the role of lighthouse cities, showcasing best practices and innovative solutions in the sector.

Both lighthouses and fellow cities face similar challenges in social housing, including aging buildings, financial pressures, housing shortages and affordability concerns. Many older buildings require significant investment to meet modern energy efficiency and accessibility standards. Securing enough funding, encouraging cooperation between public and private sectors and effectively implementing policies remain key difficulties. However, cities are increasingly prioritizing retrofitting efforts, integrating climate and social objectives, and leveraging European and national funding mechanisms to improve housing conditions.

SUPERSHINE lighthouse cities, Denmark, Italy, and Latvia, offer unique strengths in social housing, serving as models for innovation and best practices. Denmark's approach emphasizes strong tenant participation, homelessness solutions, mixed-income policies, sustainability, and crisis response, creating a resilient and inclusive housing system. Italy stands out for its cooperative housing model, integrated social services, income-based rent system, and renovation policies, ensuring long-term affordability and social cohesion. Latvia, on the other hand, demonstrates the effectiveness of municipal-led management, innovative funding mechanisms, and energy-efficient infrastructure, providing stability for low-income residents.

At the same time, these lighthouse cities provide great examples that other cities can learn from and apply to their own housing policies. Their best practices can guide fellow cities in adapting and scaling successful strategies by tailoring them to their local socio-economic and regulatory contexts. Through replication and knowledge exchange, cities can implement tested solutions, fostering a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient approach to social housing.

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